

Angiospermic Plants of Tulsi Amrit Sansthan Campus , Kanore Udaipur (Rajasthan)

Pavan Kumar harsana

Rajasthan Vidyapeeth Udaipur

Abstract - Plant taxonomy is the branch of sciences which is concerned with the identification, classification and nomenclature of the plants of particular area or region. It is one of the most important branches of plant sciences, plant taxonomy and plant systematics are related to each other, there are no clear difference between the two branches, Plant systematics is the evolutionary relationship between the plants, whereas plant Taxonomy is the actual handling of the plants in nature. However both the branches are intricately related to each other. In plant taxonomy basically three systems of classification are used, they are artificial, natural and phylogenetic classification. Plants are very important not only for humans but also for other lives on earth, life on earth is can not possible without plants. Plants supply food to all humans as well as many other living organisms on the earth, plants maintain the atmosphere, by the process of photosynthesis on the earth's gaseous balance occurs in nature. In nature biogeochemical cycles complete by the plants and their metabolism. Plants are a habitat for many organisms on earth. Plants provides humans timber, firewood, fiber, medicines, other substances. A Flora is the systematic enumeration of the plant species occurring in a region. A flora can cover a large geographical region, a district, state, country even a continent. A flora may contain a simple description of the plants of that region to the detailed account of the plants. Deforestation is the big reason for the degradation of the floristic wealth of any area. Increasing anthropogenic activity are the again major causes for the degradation of the flora's of any region. Conservation efforts are necessary for protection of the plants species in relevant Here in this research article we are presenting preliminary studies on the flora of the Tulsi Amrit Sansthan, Kanore Udaipur in rainy season a number of the herbs, shrubs, trees grown in campus and enhances the beauty of the area.

Keywords - Floristic Diversity, Kanore Udaipur Rajasthan, anthropogenic activities, urbanization, flora, exploitation, conservation.

I. INTRODUCTION

From ancient times, human beings depend on plants for their survival; the humans are directly depending on plants for their food, shelter, and medicine (Bhandari, 1978). Plants are very important elements on the earth for ecological balances in the form of biogeochemical cycles as well as majority of the economic important plants (Meena, 2012). Their distribution depends on the geographical conditions and geo climatic conditions (Parmer & Singh, 1982). It is estimated that on earth ten millions species of plants inhabit the earth, among them 1.7 million species are known to sciences (Pandey & Shetty, 1984). India has a very rich biodiversity of plants in

different ecological communities, it is estimated that India has about 45000 plant species, among them 8000 plant species are known to be the medicinal values. A huge number of flora is available in different biogeographic regions of India (Prasad, 2014).

However many of the plant species are under threat and they are near to endangered or extinct due to several anthropogenic factors and changed ecosystems (Sarup, 1952). In addition to the manmade factors there are some natural factors like herbivore, pathogens and climate changes which decline the population of the plants in that area (Sharma & Tyagi, 1979). Many plant species are extincting even before their discovery (Sharma,

2005). In the current scenario it is very urgent to protect and conserve these plants as well as animals life for successful cycling of the ecosystem (Shetty & Singh, 1987). To study the flora of the state, a small attempt has been done to study the flora of the Tulsi Amrit Sansthan campus. Different morphological features are studied like roots, stem, leaves their number, morphology, habits in addition reproductive features are also studied here calyx, corolla androecium, gynoecium being studied (Saldana, 1984). Floristic studies are useful in study of the structure, evolution an endemism & evolution of the flora of the area (Shetty & Singh, 1993).

Material and Methods Area under Study:

The present study was laid down in the Tulsi Amrit Sansthan Kanore Udaipur Rajasthan.

The Sansthan is situated in the Kanore region of Udaipur district. Kanore is situated on the Pratapgarh road at a distance of about 70 Kilometers from Udaipur. The campus is rich with floral diversity and spread on about 10 acres. The campus is known for excellence of education. The campus has fairly excellent diverse ecological settings. The campus is located in scarce vegetation due to dry weather types in the area.

The Tulsi Amrit Sansthan Kanore has rich and diverse kinds of plant communities which are of several ethno botanical importance.

Methods of Study:

The plant materials were selected carefully from the field, we did not collect species which are endangered and rare, and in many cases a part of the plants was selected rather than complete plants. The areas where plant species are prevalent we collect the complete plants from area.

The collection details such as date, place, important plant character were noted. All the observed plant species were listed according to their systematic position with vernacular names. The collected plant

specimens were identified by the taxonomic literature.

Result and Discussion:

In present investigation, which deals with study of vegetation in the Tulsi Amrit Sansthan campus, Kanore, a total of 50 plant species have been recorded based on the botanical literature. we exclude Algae, bryophytes, pteridophytes and angiosperms from the list.

A perusal of table-1 depicts that the recorded plant species belong to 50 plant families. Among the recorded plant families, the dominant family is Poaceae which is represented by mainly 10 plant species. The present study shows that campus of Tulsi Amrit Sansthan Kanore Udaipur is rich with the vascular flora, the floristic composition is dominated by the angiosperms.

A higher proportion of the flora is represented by the ornamental plants which are basically trees and shrubs. In the present studies each plants in the campus is carefully studied with also their future prospection. Many of these plants are used by adjoining tribal communities of Kanore tehsil for their primary healthcare treatment of diseases (WHO, 2002). There are few herbs which are used for the treatment of disorders of digestive system liver, Skin disease, diabetes cardiovascular system by the tribal communities. These herbs, shrubs, trees are the sources of antioxidants for treatment of free reactive oxygen. (Yoganarasimhan, 2000).

Expression of Gratitude :

Thankful to Shri Kalyan Singh ji Pokharna, Sanchalak, and Mr. Hemant ji patel sir, Mr. Prdeep Raj ji Chouhan, Mr. Janak Singh ji chundawat, Mr. Radheshyam ji sevak, Mr. imran ji hussain Mr. devkinnandan ji, Mr. Rajesh ji vaya, Sooraj Meena ji and all staff members of Tulsi Amrit Sansthan Kanore (Rajasthan) for offering access to library and laboratory and campus facilities...

Table1: List of plant species in the Tulsi Amrit sansthan campus, Kanore (Udaipur)

S.N.	BOTANICAL NAME	COMMAN NAME	FAMILY
1.	<i>Aegle marmelos</i>	Beal / Beal patra	Rutaceae
2.	<i>Albizia lebbeck</i>	Siris	Fabaceae
3.	<i>Butea monosperma</i>	Palash/ Dhak	Fabaceae
4.	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	Amaltash	Fabaceae
5.	<i>Dalbergia sissoo</i>	shisam	Fabaceae
6.	<i>Embelica officinalis</i>	Aamla	Euphorbiaceae
7.	<i>Ficus benghalensis</i>	Bargad	Moraceae
8.	<i>Morus alba</i>	Shahtoot	Moraceae
9.	<i>Ficus religiosa</i>	pipal	Moraceae
10.	<i>Musa paradisiaca</i>	Banana	Musaceae
11.	<i>Gossypium hirsutum</i>	Kapas	Malvaceae
12.	<i>Prosopis cineraria</i>	Khejrdi	Fabaceae
13.	<i>Phoenix sylvestris</i>	Khajur	Arecaceae
14.	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i>	Karanj	Fabaceae
15.	<i>Pidum guajava</i>	Jamphal	myrtaceae
16.	<i>Ficus benghalensis</i>	Bargad	moraceae
17.	<i>Syzygium cumini</i>	Jamun	myrtaceae
18.	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	neem	Meliaceae
19.	<i>Tamarindus indica</i>	Imli	Fabaceae
20.	<i>Saraca asoca</i>	Ashok	Leguminosae
21.	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Aam	Anacardaceae

Herbs

S.N.	BOTANICAL NAME	COMMAN NAME	FAMILY
1.	Aloe vera	Ghrit kumari	Asphodelaceae
2.	Catharanthus roseus (Linn.)	Sadabahar	Apocynaceae
3.	Calotropis procera	Akra	Asclepiadiaceae
4.	Coriandrum sativumL	Corinder	Asteraceae
5.	Cynodon dactylon	Doob	Poaceae
6.	Eclipta alba	Bhringraj	Euphorbiaceae
7.	Cyperus rotundus	Nagarmotha	Cyperaceae
8.	Tridax procumbens	Coat button	Asteraceae
9.	Jasminum sambac	Mogra	Oleaceae
10.	Ocimum sanctum	Tulsi	Lamiaceae
11.	Sonchus asper Hill	Dudhi	Asteraceae
12.	Phyllanthus niruri	Bhumi amla	Euphorbiaceae
13.	Rosa indica	Gulab	Rosaceae
14.	Bouteloua dactyloides (Nutt.) Columbus	Lawn grass	Graminae
15.	Tridax procumbens	Gorkhmundi	Asteraceae

Shrubs

S.N.	BOTANICAL NAME	COMMAN NAME	FAMILY
1.	Adhatoda vasica Nees	Adusa	Acanthaceae
2.	Alstonia scholaris (L.) R. Br.	Satpatti	Apocynaceae
3.	Calotropis procera (Aiton) W.T. Aiton	Aak	Asclepiadiaceae

4.	<i>Datura metal L.</i>	Dhatura	Solanaceae
5.	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	Danda Thor	Euphorbiaceae
6.	<i>Hibiscus rosa- sinensis</i>	China rose	Malvaceae
7.	<i>Lawsonia inermis</i>	Mehandi	Lythraceae
8.	<i>Murraya paniculateL.</i>	Bux/ Kamini	Rutaceae
9.	<i>Nerium spp.L.</i>	Oleander / Kaner	Apocynaceae
10.	<i>Nyctanthes arbor-tristisL.</i>	Harsingar Parijat	Nyctaginaceae
11.	<i>Plumeria rubraL.</i>	Deshi Champa	Apocynaceae

Climbers

S.N.	BOTANICAL NAME	COMMAN NAME	FAMILY
1.	<i>Rhynchosia minima (L.)</i>	Teen patti	Fabaceae
2.	<i>Cestrum nocturnumL.</i>	Raat Rani	Solanaceae
3.	<i>Bougainvillea spectabilis Willd.</i>	Great bougainvillea	Nyctaginaceae
4.	<i>Tinospora cordifolia.</i>	Giloy	Menispermaceae

III. CONCLUSION

Human life directly depends on the flora and fauna of the specific area, the survival of human life depends on the specific products obtained from the plants and animals from that area. Plants have several benefits like food, medicines, fuel, aesthetic, ecological role in that area (Sharma, 1986). Plant resources are depleting due to deforestation, and increasing anthropogenic activities, many of the important plant species are near to extinction due to degraded habitat of that area so we have to conserve the flora of that area by national and international efforts, these kinds of floristic studies are helpful in the analysis of the vegetation of that area as well as their utility for human beings. Present study highlighted plant biodiversity in the Tulsi Amrit Sansthan Kanore. The study resulted in identification and documentation of 40 plants. The campus including Botanical garden may be further used to

protect important plant species of general and medicinal uses.

REFERENCE

1. Bhandari, M.M. (1978). Flora of the Indian desert, 1- 471. (2ed. 1990).
2. Jain S.K., Rao R.R.(1977). A hand book of field and herbarium methods. Today and Tomorrow's Printers and Publishers, New Delhi, pp. 1-157.
3. Meena, K. L. (2012). Angiospermic diversity of District Bhilwara from Rajasthan, India. Photon 112, 193-204.
4. Parmar P J and Singh A N (1982). A contribution to the flora of Bhilwara District, Rajasthan J Econ Taxon Bot 7(1) 55-67.
5. Pandey R P and Shetty B V(1984). The flora of Pali district Rajasthan, India. J Econ Taxon Bot 5(2) 225-378.
6. Prasad, R. (2014) Studies on the diversity of the Tree species in the Ramgarh Vishdhari Wildlife Sanctuary Bundi, Rajasthan, Asian Resonance 3(1):53-54.
7. Sharma S and Tiagi B (1979). Flora of NorthEast Rajasthan, Kalyani Publishers, NewDelhi.
8. Sharma, O.P. (2005) Pteridophytic flora of Bundi district, southeastern Rajasthan, Zoos' print Journal 20(4):1836-1837.
9. Shetty, B.V. & V.Singh, (1993) Flora of Rajasthan Vol.III. Flora of India ser.2. Botanical Survey of India, Howarah.
10. Saldana C.J.(1984). Flora of Karnataka, Vol I, Oxford and IBH publishing Co., Mumbai.
11. Sharma, N.K. (1986) Taxonomical and phytosociological studies on vegetation of Jhalawar and its environs, Ph.D. Thesis University of Rajasthan, Jaipur.
12. WHO. Traditional Medicine: Growing Needs and Potential(2002). WHO Policy Perspectives on Medicines. World Health Organization, Geneva.